

Accession Number: P534462

19 mar 2018

Patient ID: P32481

Optima CT660

Exam Description: TERMOABLAZIONE RF - Os

Report Dose

Series	Type	Scan Range (mm)	CTDIvol (mGy)	DLP (mGy-cm)	Phantom cm
1	Scout	-	-	-	-
2	Helical	190.750-1492.000	4.90	228.22	Body 32
3	Helical	1130.750-1523.250	4.90	223.84	Body 32
4	Helical	1120.000-1165.000	4.32	47.30	Body 32
5	Helical	1120.000-1165.000	4.30	47.07	Body 32
6	Helical	1120.000-1165.000	4.33	47.31	Body 32
7	Helical	1120.000-1165.000	4.32	47.28	Body 32
8	Helical	1120.000-1165.000	4.33	47.31	Body 32
9	Helical	1120.000-1165.000	4.32	47.29	Body 32
10	Helical	1120.000-1165.000	4.32	47.27	Body 32

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Series	Type	Scan Range (mm)	CTDIvol (mGy)	DLP (mGy-cm)	Phantom cm
11	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.30	47.04	Body 32
12	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.32	47.20	Body 32
13	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.32	47.25	Body 32
14	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.31	47.09	Body 32
15	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.32	47.21	Body 32
16	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.31	47.10	Body 32
17	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.32	47.30	Body 32
18	Helical	I120.000-I165.000	4.33	47.36	Body 32
19	Helical	I130.000-I160.000	4.21	39.75	Body 32
20	Helical	I130.000-I160.000	4.21	39.71	Body 32

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Series	Type	Scan Range (mm)	CTDIvol (mGy)	DLP (mGy-cm)	Phantom cm
21	Helical	I130.000-I160.000	4.21	39.76	Body 32
22	Helical	I130.000-I160.000	4.21	39.71	Body 32
23	Helical	I130.000-I160.000	4.19	39.50	Body 32
Total Exam DLP:				1358.88	